

Tunneling Short Course
Afternoon Session on Underground Transportation Infrastructure
1:00 – 5:00 PM, October 17, 2019
Petroleum Hall, Green Center
Colorado School of Mines

Below is the program for the “*Afternoon Session on Underground Transportation Infrastructure*” as part of the Annual Tunneling Short Course that will be held at Colorado School of Mines.

The presentations will summarize problems related to transportation tunnels and the emerging solutions to these problems carried out through research at the US DOT-funded University Transportation Center for Underground Infrastructure (UTC-UTI).

These presentations will be available to the participants of the Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations Short Course and members of UTC-UTI.

Time	Presentation Title and Authors
1:00 – 1:30	1. Operational Resilience of Traffic Tunnels Sandeep Khetwal, Shiling Pei and Marte Gutierrez, Colorado School of Mines
1:30 – 2:00	2a. Stochastic Analysis of Thermal Demand and Resulting Capacity Loss of Concrete Tunnel Liners Subjected to Vehicle Fires Qi Guo, Spencer Quiel and Clay Naito Lehigh University 2b. Blast Vulnerability of Drop Ceilings in Roadway Tunnels Ziyan Ouyang, Aerik Carlton, Clay Naito and Spencer Quiel, Lehigh University
2:00 – 2:30	3. The Effect of Hybrid Reinforcement of Recycled Tire Fibers and Recycled Carbon Fibers on the Properties of Self Consolidating Concrete Siavash Fakhretaha Aval, Mehran Mazari and Tona Rodriguez, Cal State University Los Angeles
2:30 – 3:00	4. Examination of Segmental Liner Loading for Soft Ground Tunnels: Design Approaches vs. Actual Behavior Tamir Epel, Mike Mooney and Marte Gutierrez, Colorado School of Mines
3:00 – 3:30	Coffee Break
3:30 – 4:00	5. Using Deep Neural Networks to Predict Sensor Response and Geology Ahead of a TBM Kabir Nagrecha, Luis Fisher Jr., Mehran Mazari, Tona Rodriguez-Nikl and Mohammad Pourhomayoun, Cal State University Los Angeles
4:00 - 4:30	6. Feasibility Study of the Future Extension of the Eisenhower-Johnson Memorial Tunnel Gauen Alexander, Ashton Krajnovich Hui Lu and Marte Gutierrez, Colorado School of Mines
4:30 – 5:00	7. The Characterization of Delamination Processes with Respect to Waterjet Shotcrete Removal during Tunnel Liner Repair and Maintenance Hugh Miller, Erik Charrier, Josef Bourgeois, John Steele and Brian Asbury, Colorado School of Mines
5:00	Reception